

Making Nutrition a Development Priority in North Africa

JOURNAL SUBMISSION POLICY

OF

THE NORTH AFRICAN JOURNAL OF FOOD AND
NUTRITION RESEARCH (NAJFNR)

(JUNE 2018)

Manuscripts' Submission Process

Practical Guidelines for Authors

The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research

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Chapter 1. Status of the Journal

Article 1: *The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research* (NAJFNR) is a journal dedicated to the scientific community, with an international editorial board.

Article 2: The NAJFNR is an open access journal (Open Access), which publishes original research articles, review articles and synthesis as well as clinical studies in all fields of nutrition and metabolism.

Article 3: The specific topics covered in the review include:

1. Effect of Nutrition on Metabolic Control
2. Epidemiology, and the Prevalence of Related Disorders such as Obesity, Diabetes, Dyslipidemias, etc.
3. Biochemistry and Cellular Metabolism of Nutrients
4. Dietary Strategies and Nutrition Education
5. Food Security and Challenges
6. Food Behavior and Quality of Life
7. Public Health Policy & Health Economics
8. Nutrition and Cancer
9. Food Chemistry and Engineering
10. Human and Clinical Nutrition
11. Food Processing and Packaging
12. Occupational Nutrition and Medicine
13. Nutrition and Sport
14. Infant, Child, and Adolescent Nutrition
15. Nutrition and Immune Regulation

Article 4: NAJFNR is currently half-yearly basis. However, certain issues may be published in special numbers.

Article 5: The publication of articles is free and requires no pre-payment.

Chapter 2. Responsibilities

Article 6: NAJFNR is the responsibility of the Editor-in-Chief.

Article 7: The NAJFNR's editorial board consists of **Editor-in-Chief (EiC)**, **Specialty Editors (SE)**, **Associate Editors (AE)**, and **Review editors (RE)**, composed of leading experts (Professors and Associate professors) in accordance with the areas of interest of the journal. Articles submitted for publication in the journal are primarily assessed by EiC and SE according to the area of competence of the members.

Article 8: The role of Specialty and Associate Editors are mentioned on the Editorial Members' Guide (cf. Website).

Chapter 3. Submission of Articles

Article 9: The articles submitted to NAJFNR must be written in American English.

Article 10: Submission of articles to the journal is exclusively electronically to the following email address : najfnr@najfnr.org .

The article must be accompanied by the four (04) forms on the website in the section devoted to the submission "Submission" <https://www.najfnr.org/submission>. That is to say: "Covering Letter" "Authorship" the model of the "Manuscript" and "Copyright Form" in Microsoft Word version ".docx" or "PDF" format.

Article 11: After receiving the manuscript a confirmation is then sent electronically by the editorial office to the corresponding author and co-authors.

Article 12: The Editor-in-chief and a Specialty Editor are then responsible for carrying out a first reading of articles submitted over a period of **(03 days)** in order to make:

- Checking the conformity of the content according to the journal aims and scopes;
- Determine the scope and suggest appropriate associate editors;

After that the corresponding author will be notified by email that the article was intended to expertise "Peer Review" under the code (NAJFNR-xxxx) and by the Editor-in-Chief. Otherwise the Editor-in-chief should:

- Request that the article be reformulated;
- Send a rejection notification explaining the reasons.

Chapter 4. Assessment Steps

Article 13: The manuscripts selected after the first reading, will then be sent simultaneously, in an anonymous version, to two Associate Editors (AE), who should at least suggest two Review Editors (RE) who review the selected manuscript for a period of **(15 days)**.

Article 14: The review editors appointed shall notify their receipt and acceptance to review the submitted manuscript by the deadline set in the art. 13 **(15 days)**. Otherwise the Editor-in-Chief with an Associate Editor will suggest other experts of the same speciality.

Article 15: The corresponding author will be contacted to provide names of referees in the same field which will then be contacted by the Editor-in-Chief for possible reviewing.

Article 16: The NAJFNR strongly opposes the practice of duplicate publication or plagiarism of any kind. If the "Reviewers" suspect a practice in ethics in the submitted manuscript, they should mention it in the report with proof / web links.

Article 17: Member of the Editorial Board (*Reviewers*) must ensure that all sections of the article must comply with the instructions to authors are:

- **Material and methods:** "*Review Editors*" must provide feedback on the relevance and the technical standards of methods used. Sufficient details of methods used or techniques should be provided to be reproduce by other researchers;
- **Results and discussion:** "*Review Editors*" should provide comments on:
 - ➔ The quality of data if they are reliable and consistent;
 - ➔ Authors should provide relevant and updated references;
 - ➔ Discussions and conclusions should be based on real facts and figures.
 - ➔ Are the statistical analyzes necessary to this document? In the affirmative case, are they sufficient and appropriate? To this end, we should refer to statistics reviewers;
- **Conclusion:** Is the given conclusion supported by discussed data in the manuscript? The conclusions should not be biased and should be based only on the data presented in the manuscript.
- **References:** Are the cited references relevant and adequate? Are there more recent and appropriate references that the authors should cite?
- **Criticism:** The NAJFNR believes in constructive criticism. *Review Editors* are encouraged to be honest but not abusive in their language (unnecessarily harsh words might be changed and removed). We expect that review editors suggest to authors how can-they strengthen their work to make it acceptable. The reviewers' comments should be sufficiently informative and useful to reach a decision. We strongly recommend that a negative examination explains the weaknesses of any manuscript, so that the concerned authors can understand the basis of rejection and how they can improve the manuscript from those comments. Authors should not confuse simple and real comments with unfair criticism.
We are very reluctant to go against the suggestions (especially on the technical aspects) of the review editors. Therefore, authors are invited to address suggestions from reviewers of the highest importance.

NB. Rejected manuscripts have the possibility of being formally recalled. The Appeals must be in writing, not by phone, and must be submitted to najfnr@najfnr.org with one entitled "**Appeal**" in the subject line. If an author remains dissatisfied, he (she) may refer the matter to the Editor-in- Chief providing the ID of the manuscript. In all cases, it is likely that some time elapses before the NAJFNR can respond, recalling that the manuscript should not be submitted for publication elsewhere during this time. Authors must provide detailed reasons for the appeal and answer point by point to comments from Review

editors and / or the Editor-in-Chief. Authors should also be aware that priority is given to new submissions to the journal and therefore the processing of the appeal may well take longer than the processing of the original submission. If an appeal is dismissed, further appeals from the decision will not be considered and the document cannot be resubmitted.

Article 18: After expertise, review editors should send the comments (*Review Form*) cf. NAJFNR Website: <http://www.najfnr.org/reviewers>.

Article 19: If a rejection or an acceptance are sent by the review editors, without comments and motives, the report will not be considered.

Article 20: After receiving the comments, a final decision will be made by the Editor-in-Chief and one of the Specialty editors on the basis of opinion provided by Review editors:

- a. If both opinions are *favorable*, the manuscript will be "**Accepted**" for possible publication;
- b. If both opinions are *unfavorable*, the manuscript will be "**Rejected**";
- c. If the two opinions are *contradictory*, the article will be submitted to a third assessment for a period of **(15 days)** which ends the final decision.

For this purpose, the two review editors will be notified in order to justify the final decision.

Article 21: The corresponding author and co-authors will be notified of the decision on their submission.

Article 22: If the manuscript requires minor or major revisions, authors will send a corrected version within **(7 days)** from the date of notification. They must, in this case, answer questions and fill in the 3rd column for authors on the "*Review Form*" to respond to comments of "*Reviewers*". This corrected version will then be forwarded to the experts, at the first stage, for a final evaluation.

Article 23: Upon completion of final assessment, the review editor must send the result with the following information:

- a. "**ARTICLE PUBLISHED**" if reservations are lifted and authors have met all or most of the questions comments and questions;
- b. "**ARTICLE TO REFORMULATE**" in the case where changes made are not sufficient and the reviewers are not satisfied.

In this case, the manuscript is returned to the corresponding author, to undergo the same conditions set in art. 22.

Article 24: After a second reading, if the manuscript receives two (02) favorable opinions (see Art 20 a.), the Editorial Board will include it in a future issue.

Article 25: In case there would still undrawn reserves, the manuscript will be sent to authors for a third (final) reading.

Article 26: If the reserves remain, the article will automatically be marked "**Rejected.**"

Article 27: It should be mentioned that Editor-in-chief may settle for a sufficiently motivated rejection if a review editor rejects a submitted manuscript.

Article 28: The articles selected for publication in the next issue should be the subject of a final reading by the Specialty Editors with a version "**PROOF**" sent to the corresponding author to make a final reading which should not exceed 48 hours **(2 days)**.

Article 29: The online publication of selected manuscripts will be done systematically after "**PROOF**".

Article 30: The Editorial Board is required to send an electronic copy of the article to the authors for review.

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NAJFNR Review process

Chapter 5. Canceling the Submission

Article 31: The corresponding author, with the consent of co-authors can proceed with the cancellation of the manuscript submission at any stage of the treatment provided that this is done before the final notification of acceptance. The Specialty and Associate editors must validate the reasons for cancellation in order to approve the application and withdraw the manuscript definitively and must inform all the co-authors of the cancellation.

Article 32: The Editorial Board may also proceed with the cancellation of the submission when the author does not answer to three (3) reminders of the Editorial Board requesting it to additional information.

Chapter 6. Confidentiality

Article 33: All the editorial members are subject to the obligation of absolute confidentiality of manuscripts submitted to the editorial. It is therefore strictly forbidden to disclose any information, contents, whole or partial, being evaluated or rejected.

Chapter 7. Anonymity

Article 34: The anonymity of Review editors and authors should be guaranteed by Specialty and Associate editors along the assessment procedure. The manuscripts should be sent anonymously to the reviewers. The evaluation sheets (*Review Form*) will also be sent anonymously to the authors.

Chapter 8. Plagiarism and Self-Plagiarism

Article 35: Plagiarism is a way of appropriating the creative work of someone else and present it as his own; to extract text, images, data, etc., from external sources and integrate them into their own work without mentioning the source; Summarize the original idea of an author by expressing it in his own words, but omitting to mention the source. Duplicate publication, called auto-plagiarism, occurs when an author re-uses substantial parts of his or her own published work without providing the appropriate references. This can range from obtaining an identical article published in several journals, where the authors add small amounts of new data to a previous article.

Article 36: It is set to the availability of reviewers of the plagiarism detection tools on the official website of the journal at the following address: <http://www.najfnr.org/reviewers>.

Chapter 9. Assessment Difficulties

Article 37: After a period of 60 days (**2 months**) from the manuscript receipt, if the Editorial Board meet assessment difficulties of the submitted manuscript or lack of availability of (*Reviewers*) in the field, the corresponding author should be notified to:

- inform authors of the situation and encountered difficulties;
- offer the possibility as follows:
 - ➔ Reformulation of the submitted manuscript;
 - ➔ Maintain the submitted manuscript;
 - ➔ Removing the submitted manuscript.

Article 38: If the authors decide to keep the article, an additional term (**2 months**) is granted for possible evaluation.

Article 39: The Editorial Board can be satisfied only by one notice of acceptance or rejection to make final decision for manuscripts reporting difficulties of assessment.

Article 40: If the assessment is still not issued in time, as stated in the conditions of art. 37, the editorial may proceed to the cancellation of the submitted manuscript.

Chapter 10. Miscellaneous

Article 41: An article published in "Proceeding" older than 2 years is not accepted for submission.

Article 42: An article rejected after the assessment stage, will be resubmitted after having completely changed the title and content. This is the privilege of the Editorial board for review before it is sent to review editors.

Article 43: Any change in the list of authors of a paper submitted to the journal must be submitted to the approval of the Editorial Board.

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